

Beyond MOOCs: Reclaiming Open Education

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MOOCs aren't MOOCs

networked learning exploration > instructional industry
educational experiment, event > content distribution model

Purpose: educational and commercial

Place: online and blended

License: copyrighted and OER

Software: Proprietary and Open Source

Access: gratis and payed

Prerequisites: none/open to some/closed

Rythm: self-paced and scheduled

Time: sync and assync

Certification: with and without

Assessment: none, self, peer, auto and exams

Media: trans and video-only

Network: PirateBay and NetFlix

Interactive and enteractive

MOOCs aren't Open Education

MOOCs aren't for all (educated part, 2/5 of world pop, paying), massive dropouts, automatic assessment, freeware (marketing, branding) or freemium (fees for premium services), downsize the teaching staff (bye bye PCK), ...

undermine public education and education for all...

"(...) we fear that two classes of universities will be created: one, **well-funded colleges and universities in which privileged students get their own real professor**; the other, financially **stressed private and public universities in which students watch a bunch of video-taped lectures** and interact, if indeed any interaction is available on their home campuses, with a professor that this model of education has turned into a glorified teaching assistant".

"Open Letter to Professor Michael Sandel From the Philosophy Department at San Jose State University"

and WHAT is Open Education?

Umbrella term for a social movement that supports the “development of knowledge cultures based on non-proprietary modes of knowledge production and exchange” (Peters, 2012).

FREE (commons) and **OPEN** (social production)

and WHERE is Open Education?

Track, organize, share, and validate educational achievements, including formal, informal and experiential learning.

Open Courseware and Support
Create and help schools adopt OER
OER and learning analytics

Tuition-free, accredited, online academic courses.
Registration fee (\$10-\$50)+ exam fee (\$100)
(Bachelor Degree = \$4,000)

Formal academic credit OER learning in
partnership with a university network.
Pay reduced fees for assessment and credit.

Digital badges to recognize skills and achievements
inside or outside the classroom.
Metadata (badge issuer, criteria, etc.)
Can be issued by anyone.

and WHERE is Open Education?

Explore and (re)invent and (re)discover educational practices (also formal education) that explore the dynamics of peer production, co-production and co-design (content, curricula, assessment), collaboration.

Course (stand-alone, facilitated, mechanical mooc or course-in-a-box)

Peer-support, creativity and production, transmedia, student-designed assignments, learning in public, open network, decentralized hub, DIY.

Learning Circles
(study group)

and **WHERE** to go?

Let's **FSCCK** the MOOCs

Let's conspire and get together for a

Creative

Open and

Free

Fruitful

Educational

Experience

Thank you for your attention!

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P2PU - <https://www.p2pu.org/en/>

DS106 - <http://ds106.us/>